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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D7.3 – Recommendations toward the development of IWT including medium- term forecast of navigability conditions

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

Document summary information

Grant Agreement No	101069838	Acronym	CRISTAL
Full Title	Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways		
Start Date	01/09/2022	Duration	40 months
Project URL	http://www.cristal-project.eu/		
Deliverable	D7.3 Recommendations toward the development of IWT including medium-term forecast of navigability conditions.		
Work Package	WP7		
Contractual due date	30/11/2025	Actual submission date	31/12/2025
Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Participant	AIPo		

Revision history

Version	Issue Date	Complete %	Changes	Contributor(s)
V0.1	20/12/2025	90%	Chapters 1-7	AIPo
V0.2	22/12/2025	95%	Peer Review	Fraunhofer
V0.3	29/12/2025	98%	Incorporation of comments and suggestions	AIPo
V0.4	30/12/2025	100%	Final Version	UniTra
V1.0	30/12/2025	100%	Final verification	Marta Cudziło (L-PIT)

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AGN	Agreement on Main Inland Waterways of International importance
Aipo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CNC	Core Network Corridors of TEN-T
EU	European Union
FEWS	Flood Early Warning System
GA	Grant Agreement
HW	Hardware
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Waterway
KET	Key enabling technologies
KPI	Key performance indicator
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MIT	Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport
ML	Machine Learning
NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
O	Objective
PRP	Po River Pilot
RIS	River Information Services
SB	Smart Bulletin
SCMS	Syncro-modal Corridor Management System
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SW	Software
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

The main objective of the report is to focus on the contents of paragraph 3.5 "Navigability Conditions Forecasting Model and Smart Bulletin" contained within Deliverable D7.2¹. This Deliverable provides an in-depth look at the different phases that lead to the generation of the Smart Bulletin, starting from the external sensors, the functional requirements that defined the structure of both the statistical and machine learning models, and the APIs that allow the output data of the models to be sent both to the Smart Bulletin generator and to the SCMS created by CERT.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

This section provides an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable & corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of 7.3 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.3 Recommendations toward the development of IWT including medium-term forecast of navigability conditions	<i>Aim of the pilot</i>	<i>Chapter 2 General overview Chapter 3 Specific objectives</i>	<i>The chapter 2 briefly illustrates a general overview of the Po River Pilot The chapter 3 illustrate the general and the specific objectives of the navigability prediction model and of the smart bulletin</i>
	<i>Results of the pilot</i>	<i>Chapters 4, 5, 6</i>	<i>Chapters 4 describes the main characteristics of the statistical model and of the Machine Learning. Chapter 5 describes the functional requirements, the Software and</i>

¹ See D7.2 Po River Pilot solution descriptions, test results and impact assessment.

			<p><i>Hardware structure of the Smart Bulletin</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 6 illustrates the final result and the KPI related to the Smart Bulletin.</i></p>
	<p><i>Conclusions and Recommendations</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 7</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 7 is dedicated to the conclusions and recommendations</i></p>
<p>TASKS</p>			
<p>Task 7.1 Pilot supervision, concept assessment and coordination with WP6</p>	<p><i>On the basis of the scenario set in WP1, the solutions proposed by WP2, WP3, WP5 and the input from WP6, the set of technologies and system to be tested in the Po River pilot will be identified with the related monitoring technique and KPI.</i></p>	-	
<p>Task 7.2 Engineering and implementation: New forecasting navigability model and green port cold ironing</p>	<p><i>This task is addressing:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>• The realisation of a prediction model for Po river navigability conditions</i> <i>• The study for the realization of a network of cold ironing facilities along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo channel including a dedicated designing model guidelines and a related masterplan for the implementation</i> 	<p><i>Chapters 3,4,5</i></p> <p>-</p>	<p><i>Description of models developed to achieve the Smart Bulletin, of the functional requirements, and of the final results.</i></p>
<p>Task 7.3 Corridor management & organisational models for sustainability,</p>	<p><i>This task will implement different applications of WP3 Corridor management:</i></p>	-	

resilience and competitiveness of the territorial synchromodal transport system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A new smart daily report navigability conditions. 		
Task 7.4 Governance: Living labs activation and management	<p>Setting up a sustainable stakeholder’s partnership for longer term collaboration through the living lab concept in order to develop a resilient, more competitive and more entrepreneurial regional inland waterways transport and logistic economy.</p>	-	
Task 7.5 Digital twin		-	

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This report is structured in six main chapters.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the importance of the Po River Pilot to improve the technological equipment and sustainability of inland waterways.

Chapter 3 offers a detailed explanation of general and specific objectives of the Smart Bulletin.

Chapter 4 describes the models developed to generate the Smart Bulletin. The statistical model is based on data collected at over 160 critical points along the Po, allowing for a statistical assessment of navigability in terms of probability. The machine learning-based model allows for predictions of water depth and integration of the results of the statistical model.

Chapter 5 describes the functional requirements of the smart bulletin, the phases that make up the bulletin generation process and the hardware components related to the technologies developed by the Cristal project.

Chapter 6 illustrates the results, that is the Smart Bulletin and the KPIs expected.

Chapter 7 contains conclusions and recommendations.

2. General Overview

Po river waterways are a quite complex with a free-flowing section from Piacenza to river mouth therefore, navigation is strongly influenced by the climatic conditions that can generate flooding or drought with a big impact on the reliability of the inland waterway transportation.

Climate change will produce more catastrophic events such as long periods of drought or heavy rains with the associated rapid flooding.

But the Po waterways are so important as the most ecofriendly transport system in the hearth of the most advanced economic region of Italy that cannot be missed.

Therefore, the scope of the Italian pilot is to contribute to increase the “resilience” of Northern Italy waterways reducing the impact of catastrophic events, both caused by climate change or by men, on the transport of goods and passengers also have in mind the preservation of the natural environment.

The objectives of Po River pilot (PRP) are:

- O2 - Use of state-of-the-art technologies, including digitalisation, to increase the operability and resilience of infrastructure during extreme events
 - ✓ O2.a - Increasing awareness on navigation possibilities during extreme event
 - ✓ O2.b - Increase the resilience of the overall IWW infrastructure
- O3 - Increase of the IWW transport modal shift sustainability and resilience
 - ✓ O3.a – Improving the reliability of forecasts of navigability conditions and extending the forecast period
 - ✓ O3.b - Reduce environmental impact of the overall IWW infrastructure
 - ✓ O3.c - Increasing the services to IWW operator along a quay
- O4 – Exploitation on local as well as European level and beyond.

PRP will contribute from forecasting models perspective, coupling two numerical model, a statistical model, developed by AIPo and a machine learning model, developed by ENEA, an operative system FEWS (Flood Early Warning System) and surveys data in order to provide forecast of navigability condition, such as the water depth in some critical point covering a period of 10 days, for example, that can be put in a new bulletin to IWW end-user. The main goal is to define a medium-term friendly forecast bulletin which is a decision support tool for the supply chain manager to identify the optimal mode of transport to the final destination of goods. It allows the eco-sustainable and environmentally friendly use of the Po River ecosystem.

The forecasting model will be extremely useful in case of extreme events such as low and high-water condition. In fact, based on the forecasted data, it is possible to plan in advance interventions to eliminate sandbanks formed that hinder navigation increasing the resilience of the IWW system for good transportation. Moreover, having a reliable forecast information about the situation along the Po River could be very useful to Civil Protection in order to plan its intervention, if necessary, to a possible corridor management system and also to transport and logistic operators allowing them to re-programming their transport using an alternative way (modal shift).

3. General and Specific Objectives

3.1. General Objectives – Detailed explanation

- 1. Ensure the safety of navigation**
 - The bulletin must provide reliable and timely information to prevent accidents.
 - Includes data on river depth, currents, obstacles, and weather conditions that may affect safety.
 - Goal: minimize risks for vessels, crews, and cargo.
- 2. Support activity planning**
 - Helps operators plan trips, cargo transport, and logistical operations efficiently.
 - Forecast information allows choosing the safest periods and optimizing travel times.
 - Useful for shipping companies, construction sites, and port authorities.
- 3. Reduce environmental and economic risks**
 - Prevents damage to river infrastructure and vessels.
 - Minimizes costs caused by delays, accidents, or emergency interventions.
 - Contributes to protecting the river ecosystem by avoiding floods or contamination.
- 4. Maintain continuity of river traffic**
 - Ensures the regular flow of goods and passengers.
 - Reduces interruptions due to adverse conditions or unexpected events.
 - Supports economic stability for activities dependent on river navigation.
- 5. Provide related weather information**
 - Integrates hydrological data with weather forecasts (wind, rain, fog, temperature).
 - Helps assess the impact of atmospheric conditions on manoeuvrability and safety.
 - Essential for planning during extreme weather events.

3.2. Specific Objectives – Detailed Explanation

- 1. Predict the river stage and discharge**
 - Provide forecasts of water levels and flow rates to anticipate navigability conditions.
 - Helps operators prepare for high-water or low-water scenarios that affect vessel clearance and manoeuvrability.
- 2. Indicate obstacles or restrictions**
 - Report temporary or permanent navigation hazards such as construction zones, dredging operations, bridges, or shallow areas.
 - Include any restrictions on vessel size, draft, or speed.
- 3. Provide related weather information**
 - Deliver forecasts for wind, precipitation, fog, and temperature that influence navigation safety.
 - Highlight severe weather events that may require route adjustments or delays.
- 4. Define manoeuvrability conditions**
 - Specify maximum allowed speed, current strength, turbulence zones, and visibility limitations.
 - Offer guidance for safe vessel handling under forecasted conditions.

5. Update on alerts or emergencies

- Communicate urgent warnings such as floods, ice formation, or sudden changes in river conditions.
- Ensure timely dissemination to prevent accidents and protect infrastructure.

The image below summarizes the main general and specific objectives.

Figure 1 General and specific objectives

Another extremely important specific objective is that the smart bulletin represents a support tool for the AIPO Inland Navigation Directorate, allowing it to better orient its actions, both in terms of personnel management and in terms of planning dredging activities of shallow water points.

4. Model Developed to achieve “Smart Bulletin”

4.1. Statistical Model

Since 1988, the AIPo inland navigation department has collected daily measurements of river depth at more than 160 critical points along the Po River, resulting in approximately 2 million data points, allowing a statistical evaluation of navigability in terms of probability.

Figure 2 Critical points and water level gauges
 Source: Google Maps

In addition to the measured dataset, the use of flood and drought early warning system forecasts, still available at AIPo, was considered to achieve the project goals.

Figure 3 Discharge forecasted by AIPo flood and drought models
 Source: Own elaboration

The statistical model was developed considering the following data:

- GIS information for each low-point and reaches subdivision for the entire Po River;
- A dataset of measured water depth collected daily since 1988 for several known critical points (low points);
- Historical data of water levels and derived discharges at each water level gauges.
- +10 days forecasted discharges provided by hydrological models from the Flood and Drought Early Warning System (forecast application).

The evolution of water depth data at all critical points and the related observed discharges at the nearest water level station was analysed, finding a good correlation between discharges and water depth, in fact, if we evaluate the variability of water depth at each discharge value, we can assume that the variation is closely related to morphological changes in terms of bathymetry due to flood events (e.g., solid transport, dune and ripple migration) or artificial events (e.g., dredging, hydraulic structures).

Figure 4 Historical time series of water depth and discharge
Source: Own elaboration

Joining the calculated observed and forecasted discharges (provided by monitoring network and mid-term hydrological models) at a reference station we should be able to produce a navigation probability forecast at each critical point and, using a probability threshold, a Boolean navigable / not-navigable response.

The entire dataset provides a solid basement, but historical data describe an “overall” definition of probability, in fact, the relation between discharges and water depth are influenced by artificial and natural morphological variation. To reduce the “uncertainty” related to those factors we can consider in future the introduction of the probability “conditioned” to the previous value. In fact, if we plot the data couple of water depth and discharge as a time series, we should observe a variation of the correlation for each event.

Figure 7 Temporal variation of water depth and discharge relation
Source: Own elaboration

Acceptance tests of Statistical Model

For a correct evaluation the first step is a definition of adequate metrics capable to highlight the performance for the final model goals. In the Po River case, the model should be used to provide a Boolean answer for each reach of the river, hence a binary prediction of navigable or not navigable.

For that kind of binary forecast models, a good evaluation of their performance is commonly derived by contingency table and the related indexes. A contingency table is composed of a 2x2 matrix where the axes are the model and the observed event respectively compared to a defined threshold (binary division).

Table 2 Contingency table

PO RIVER NAVIGABILITY FORECAST STATISTIC MODEL		OBSERVED		
		No	Yes	TOTAL
MODEL	No	HIT	FA	HIT+FA
	Yes	MA	CN	MA+CN
	TOTAL	HIT+MA	FA+CN	HIT+FA+CA+CN

Source: Own elaboration

Where:

- HIT – Correct forecast
- FA – False Alarm
- MA – Missed Alarm
- CN – Correct negative

The indexes derived are:

Table 3 Performance Indexes

Indexes		Formula
CSI	<i>Critical Success Index</i>	$HIT/(HIT+MA+FA)$
POD	<i>Prob. Of Detection</i>	$HIT/(HIT+MA)$
FAR	<i>False Alarm Ratio</i>	$FA/(HIT+FA)$
F	<i>False detection rate</i>	$FA/(FA+CN)$
ACC	<i>Accuracy</i>	$(HIT+CN)/(HIT+CN+FA+MA)$
SR	<i>Success Ratio</i>	$HIT/(HIT+FA)$
MAR	<i>Missed Alarm Ratio</i>	$MA/(HIT+MA)$

Source: Own elaboration

For each critical point an also for the entire dataset the complete indexes are calculated. To obtain an unbiased validation the entire dataset was divided in two different sub-sets, the calibration dataset containing all data from 2000 to 2022 and the validation dataset composed by the remaining data from 2023 to 2024.

To obtain a binary response (nav / not nav.) we fixed a probability threshold (i.e. 70%), and the overall results are the following (navigation class 140 cm, all sites):

Table 4 Observed data

PO RIVER NAVIGABILITY FORECAST STATISTICAL MODEL		OBSERVED		
		No	Yes	Total
MODEL	No	4792	10631	15.423
	Yes	746	87086	87.832
	Total	5538	97717	103.255

Source: Own elaboration

Table 5 Performance Indexes

Indexes actual		
CSI	0,296	<i>Critical Success Index</i>
POD	0,865	<i>Prob. Of Detection</i>
FAR	0,689	<i>False Alarm Ratio</i>
F	0,109	<i>False detection rate</i>
ACC	0,890	<i>Accuracy</i>
SR	0,311	<i>Success Ratio</i>
MAR	0,135	<i>Missed alarm ratio</i>

Source: Own elaboration

The overall results showed a good performance in terms of accuracy and probability of detection, although a more accurate indexes can be achieved defining not an overall but a site-specific analysis and probability threshold. In the following table, a site-specific analysis with optimized threshold is showed.

Table 6 Site specific analysis and probability threshold

REACH	CRITICAL POINT	POD	FAR	ACC	SR
CASALMAGGIORE	CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,767	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	F. PENN. GUSSOLA	1,000	0,000	0,877	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FOSSACAPRARA	0,925	0,081	0,851	0,925
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,811	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CASELLA ROSSA	0,895	0,118	0,863	0,895
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CICOGNARA	1,000	0,000	0,910	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	FRONTE CURVA N. 31	1,000	0,000	0,832	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	V. CHIAVICA TORRICELLA	0,991	0,010	0,940	0,991
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE CASALMAGGIORE	1,000	0,000	0,860	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE FOCE PARMA	1,000	0,000	0,867	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE PENNELLO COGOZZO	1,000	0,000	0,833	1,000
CASALMAGGIORE	VALLE PENNELLO SACCA	1,000	0,000	0,877	1,000

Source: Own elaboration

4.2. Machine Learning Model

A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network has been tested to predict water depth and to compare or integrate the risk results obtained using the statistical method. In particular, the work plan aimed to generate a predictor for each critical point along each river stretch. For each vessel class, given a forecast of water discharge over the next 10–15 days at each critical point within a stretch, the navigability of the entire stretch is determined by the worst predicted water depth among its critical sections.

Figure below illustrates the problem statement of the LSTM method.

Figure 8 Problem statement representation of the deep learning method

Source: Own elaboration

From the water depth forecast series, one can easily obtain the prediction of navigability for each type of vessel. However, the confidence level of such predictions should be carefully analysed to mitigate both safety-related risks, where navigation is allowed under unsafe conditions, and operational risks, where navigation is unnecessarily restricted despite safe conditions.

The research questions posed to the ML-based forecast experiments are as follows:

[RQ1] How does the LSTM navigability predictor perform on the available real data?

[RQ2] What is the quality of predictors on testing datasets?

The TensorFlow Python implementation of LSTM has been used to build the code for training and testing the models. As it is common practice for this type of software development, the best LSTM configuration has been decided empirically. The development process of the models is an iteration over the quality of the predictions on the validation data by using various metrics, including accuracy (ACC score function) and F1. The general process followed is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Development process of a prediction model

Source: Own elaboration

To answer [RQ1], this process was applied for several critical sections of the same stretch and of different stretches, selected based on the quality of the input data (e.g., completeness). Among the experiments, the setting in Table 1 led to the most accurate model for more than one critical section.

Table 7 Model configuration.

Parameter	Value
Input dataset	series water discharge series water depth timeline: days from 1 January 2002 to 31 May 2022
window size	15
normalization	z-score
LSTM sequential model settings	bidirectional layers of
	1024, 512, 256, 128, and 64 units
	adam optimizer, learning rate 0.002 20 epochs, early stopping
training-validation split	KFold cross-validation, 5-10 splits

Source: Own elaboration

The model has been trained on the two-input series (to learn patterns of correspondence of their values), and the purpose of the resulting model is to take an input sequence of some length for one of the two series (series water discharge in our experiments) and learn to predict the corresponding values of the other series. However, the trained LSTM model could be used to predict future values of both water discharge and water depth series.

To answer [RQ2], model validity can be assessed through residual-based analysis on testing datasets. This analysis allows the verification of the absence of systematic bias, the assessment of temporal stability over the testing period, and the identification of potential error patterns or outliers.

As an illustrative example of model validation, the results obtained for the Casalmaggiore Ponte Stradale site are presented in the following. The analysis focuses on the residuals computed over the testing period spanning the entire year 2022, with the training phase ending on 31 May 2022.

Figure 10 Example of model validation in Casalmaggiore Ponte stradale site
Source: Own elaboration

Residuals have been computed on normalized data. As the figure above shows, residuals are generally centred around zero and do not exhibit persistent temporal trends, indicating the absence of systematic bias and a stable predictive behaviour of the model beyond the training phase. Deviations outside ± 1 up to approximately ± 2 correspond to rarer conditions and do not indicate systematic model errors. The analysis of the residuals computed over the entire year 2023 does not show a persistent long-term drift, indicating stable model behaviour; however, for longer-term future periods, periodic retraining may be appropriate to maintain acceptable performance.

Acceptance tests of Machine Learning Model

The ultimate purpose of the models is not the precise prediction of water depth, but rather the assessment of navigability for each vessel class, i.e. determining whether the water depth exceeds a threshold related to the vessel class. To evaluate the comparative performance of the machine-learning and statistical methods for navigability prediction, a stretch of the Po River was selected, namely Revere, and predictor models were generated following the process described earlier.

The use of a common LSTM configuration across all critical sections resulted in heterogeneous performance of the generated models, reflecting site-specific characteristics rather than model configuration differences.

Figure 11 Performance of the best predictors for REVERE, based on false positive and false negative results

Source: Own elaboration

Figure 11 reports the top five models for two vessel classes (Class 140 and Class 250), selected by minimizing the sum of false positive and false negative rates. For each river section, the bars show the relative contribution of false positives and false negatives. A false positive corresponds to a case in which the model predicts navigable conditions when the river stretch is actually not navigable, while a false negative corresponds to a case in which non-navigable conditions are predicted when the stretch is in fact navigable. The results highlight a significant variability in model performance across river sections and vessel classes, even when considering only the top-performing models. The balance between false positive and false negative rates differs among sites, indicating that navigability prediction accuracy is strongly influenced by local conditions. Among the analysed sections, the model developed for Monte P. Revere achieved the lowest false negative rates for both vessel classes; since false negatives represent a particularly relevant error for navigability operations, this indicates a more reliable identification of navigable conditions at this location. Residual analysis for Monte P. Revere model over the 2022 testing

period shows that errors are generally centred around zero, indicating the absence of systematic bias. Although some clustered patterns and isolated outliers are observed during specific periods, suggesting reduced accuracy in reproducing detailed riverbed variability under particular hydrological conditions, this does not compromise the model's validity for navigability prediction. Overall, this represents an example of a model with operationally usable performance, given that its primary objective is to assess navigability thresholds rather than to achieve a precise prediction of riverbed dynamics, and that false negative rates remain consistently low.

Overall, the results obtained in this study are promising and demonstrate the potential of the proposed modelling framework to support navigability assessment. Nevertheless, there remains scope for further improvement. In particular, extending the training datasets would allow the models to better capture critical periods and evolving conditions, thereby enhancing their robustness over longer time horizons. Future developments should also explicitly account for the uncertainty associated with model outputs, especially in the context of decision-making under variable hydrological and climatic conditions. This aspect is particularly relevant when models are applied to operational scenarios or stress conditions. Finally, further analysis should focus on the lower-performing models, where the integration of domain expertise and expert knowledge can help interpret model behaviour, identify limiting factors, and guide targeted refinements. Such an approach would support more reliable and context-aware navigability predictions.

5. Functional Requirements Definition

5.1. SW Architecture

To achieve all the objectives, set out in the GA, related to the Smart Bulletin Generator, a system architecture was defined, which is schematised in the flow chart below:

Overall Structure

The diagram consists of interconnected blocks representing system components and data flows. Green arrows indicate data or information flow, while black arrows likely represent control or API integration.

Figure 12 Diagram of System components and data flow

Source: Own elaboration

The entire process to generate the Smart Bulletin is divided in the following phases:

1. Acquisition by external sensors of daily values relating to fairway depth, hydrometric values and flow rate, which will be automatically or manually entered the dB currently in use by the Inland Navigation Department developed in Access. This process, in the first instance, will lead to the generation of an NtS which, via an API, will send the information regarding any disruptions to the SCMS.
2. At the same time, an Oracle dB will be generated that will extract from the Access dB all the information necessary to populate and run both the statistical model and the ML model; the statistical model developed by AIPO will be allocated on an AIPO server, while the allocation of

the ML developed by ENEA/Fraunhofer is still to be defined (it may reside on the same server of the statistical model or in an external environment and send the results to the AIPO server through an API;

3. The results produced by the two models are acquired by a 'Decision Making Model', that is being designing, to select the navigability condition forecast results that will generate the Smart Bulletin that will also be sent to the SCMS via API.

Key Components and their Roles

1. External Sensor
 - Captures real-time environmental or hydrological data (e.g., water levels, currents, weather conditions).
 - Feeds this data into the system for processing.
2. Navigation Operator
 - Human or automated entity responsible for monitoring and managing navigation operations.
 - Receives sensor data and interacts with the navigation database.
3. Navigation dB & Oracle dB
 - Databases storing navigation-related data and operational records.
 - Oracle dB likely serves as the main repository for structured data used by analytical models.
4. Statistical Model & Machine Learning Model
 - Perform predictive analytics and pattern recognition on historical and real-time data.
 - Generate forecasts for river conditions, disruptions, and navigability.
5. Decision-Making Model
 - Uses outputs from statistical and ML models to determine operational actions.
 - Supports automated or semi-automated decision-making for navigation safety and efficiency.
6. NtS (Notices to Skippers)
 - Standardized communication tool for informing skippers about navigation conditions, restrictions, or hazards.
 - Linked to disruption management and bulletin generation.
7. Disruption
 - Represents events that affect normal navigation (e.g., floods, low water, accidents).
 - Connected to API for external communication and integration with other systems.
8. Smart Bulletin
 - Automated bulletin providing real-time updates on river conditions, alerts, and recommendations.
 - Distributed via API and published on the AIPO Website for public access.
9. SCMS (Supply Chain Management System)
 - Receives data through API to adjust logistics and transport planning based on river conditions.
 - Ensures continuity of operations despite disruptions.
10. API
 - Facilitates data exchange between internal components and external systems (e.g., SCMS, website).
 - Critical for interoperability and real-time updates.

5.2. HW Architecture

The picture below shows the high-level diagram of the subdivision into hardware components related to the part of the CRISTAL under development by AIPO. In addition to the internal components (AIPO IT system), evidence is given of the external components to which the AIPO system will have to interact through the related interface.

Figure 13 Diagram of hardware components
 Source: Own elaboration

The AIPO IT system will be composed by two distinct environments: a first environment dedicated to development; a second environment, with better hardware characteristics, dedicated to production.

Overall Structure

1. The system is represented as a large container (the main application environment) that includes several internal modules and external components connected via **APIs**. The design emphasizes interoperability and modularity.

Key Components and Their Roles

External Sensors (Gauge & Discharge)

These sensors provide real-time hydrological data such as water level (gauge) and discharge (flow rate).

Data enters the system through APIs, ensuring standardized communication.

SCMS (Supply Chain Management System)

External system that uses river condition data to adjust logistics and transport planning.

Connected via API for real-time updates.

Statistical Model & ML Model

Analytical engines that process historical and real-time data to generate forecasts and predictive insights.

Feed their outputs into the main system through API integration.

Virtual Machine (Core Processing Environment)

Hosts the main functional modules:

Data Integration: Aggregates inputs from sensors, models, and databases.

Reporting: Produces structured outputs for internal and external stakeholders.

Smart Bulletin Generator: Creates automated bulletins summarizing navigability conditions, alerts, and recommendations.

DB Server

Centralized database storing operational data, forecasts, and historical records.

Supports queries and updates from the virtual machine.

File System

Handles storage of forecast files (e.g., AIPO-Forecast in JSON format) and database access logs.

Ensures persistence and traceability of data.

APIs

Act as communication bridges between internal modules and external systems (SCMS, sensors, models).

Enable real-time data exchange and system interoperability.

The following table summarizes the characteristics of the hardware resources expected for both environments:

Table 8 Characteristics of the hardware resources

	Core (#)	RAM (GB)	HD Base (GB)	HD SSD (GB)	I 'm. ARC (GB)
Virtual Machine AS Prod.	16	32	-	100	-
Virtual Machine AS Dev.	8	16	100	-	-
DB Oracle Prod.	10	32	-	800	100
DB Oracle Dev.	8	22	700	-	100
I 'm. ARC for DB backup	-	-	-	-	1300
Total	42	102	800	900	1500

Source: Own elaboration

The Operating System provided for Virtual Machines (both for Application Servers and for databases) is Oracle Linux 8. The Oracle database version used is 19c.

6. Final Results

6.1. Smart Bulletin

The navigable part of the Po River includes a series of shallow waters point that in some hydrometric conditions, do not allow or introduce risks to navigation. The navigable part has been divided into branch within which there are various shallow waters (low depth points) potentially source of interruption of the navigability of the entire section.

To allow an adequate planning of navigation activities on the river, considering the logistical and travel problems, the availability of tools capable of providing useful information on the river navigability condition in each section, even in forecast, is essential for a correct planning and could be an attractive prospective for future developments of this sector.

The smart bulletin consists of a table with four sections of the River Po Form Cremona to Mantua. The locations represent nodes in the waterway system where interchange of goods with road or rail carriers is possible.

For each section, the navigability conditions at all critical points are reported. The lowest navigability value is selected among all the critical points on a given segment. Green indicates that all critical points in a section are navigable. The analysis is performed for each day and considering the different vessel draft classes.

Below is the Smart Bulletin in its final version:

Figure 14 Smart Bulletin_main view
 Source: Own elaboration

The Smart Bulletin is available to inland navigation users via AIPo website at the following link on a dedicated page:

<https://www.agenziapo.it/content/smart-bulletin>

Starting from the first months of 2026, the Smart Bulletin will be available from the Home Page of the AIPo website in the "Activities - "Inland Navigation" section as shown in the image below:

Figure 15 Homepage of AIPo website

Source: Own elaboration

Also from 2026, the Smart Bulletin will be downloadable from App Store and Play Store.

The "Portolano del Po" app was designed and implemented as part of the Action Plan of the UNESCO MAB Reserve "Po Grande" following a collaboration agreement between ADBPO and AIPo.

The Portolano del Po aims to provide a useful tool for discovering the Po River and navigating it safely, creating direct contact between users and the administrations involved thanks to real-time reports and updates.

Figure 16 App «THE Portolano OF RIVER Po» downloadable on App Store or Play Store
Source: Own elaboration

6.2. KPIs

The KPIs expected following the creation of the Smart Bulletin were to lead to an increase in downloads by inland navigation users of more than 20 times the normal downloads of the daily Po Riverbed Bulletin; the results showed that downloads from the AIPO website were always greater than 20.

Considering the "Portolano del Po" app in the "Bullets and Notices" section, 10% referred to downloads of the Smart Bulletin. In both cases, the Smart Bulletin was in its test form.

Pagina	Visite
Home	31252
Bollettini e Avvisi	9336
Carta nautica digitale	9086
Lista attracchi	5014
Carte del fiume Po	3606
Segnaletica e regolamento	1734
Riserve della biosfera	1724
Ponti e conche	1492
Normative di navigazione	948
Invio Segnalazioni	723
Enti promotori	568
Mappa delle riserve	422
Singolo attracco	3

Figure 17 AIPo website statistics
Source: Own elaboration

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

The CRISTAL project demonstrates that inland waterway transport (IWT) can become a more resilient and sustainable mode of transportation through the integration of advanced forecasting tools and digital solutions. The Po River pilot highlights the importance of coupling **statistical models**, **machine learning techniques**, and **hydrological forecasting systems** to provide accurate medium-term predictions of navigability conditions.

The development of a **Smart Bulletin** as a decision-support tool represents a significant step forward in improving operational planning for logistics operators, infrastructure managers, and civil protection authorities. By enabling proactive measures—such as dredging shallow areas, adjusting transport schedules, and implementing modal shifts—the system enhances both **safety and efficiency** while reducing environmental impacts.

Furthermore, the approach aligns with European objectives for climate resilience and sustainable transport, contributing to the **modal shift towards inland waterways** and supporting the achievement of **SDGs** (Sustainable Development Goals). The integration of real-time data, predictive analytics, and user-friendly communication platforms ensures that stakeholders can make informed decisions even under extreme weather conditions.

In conclusion, the proposed framework not only strengthens the reliability of IWT in Northern Italy but also provides a replicable model for other European waterways. Future work should focus on scaling the solution, improving interoperability with existing River Information Services (RIS), and incorporating additional environmental indicators to further enhance resilience and sustainability.

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